

Development of Automated Guided Vehicles for a Smart Factory: A Project-Based Learning Experience

Yasiru Shikshitha Malshan Benaragama¹, Pisut Koomsap¹

¹ Department of Industrial Systems Engineering, Asian Institute of Technology, Pathumthani, Thailand

Email: fluxes94@gmail.com, pisut@ait.asia

Abstract

Manufacturers are facing a challenge from customer demands of product variety in several small batch sizes that desperately need a flexible material handling system. This challenge stimulated the idea of developing a flexible material handling system to support student learning in an Erasmus+ Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE4.0) funded by the European Commission. It also became a Master thesis on managing a fleet of automated guided vehicles (AGVs). This paper discusses the learning experience gained over the project timeline. Several activities have been done both academic and non-academic throughout this journey of project-based learning, and from identifying the problem statement to the delivery of five in-house AGVs and their management system. Prior to the design of the five AGVs, a small prototype was built and a network was tested for proof of concept. Furthermore, a set of experiments were conducted to ensure repeatability and reproducibility can be achieved. Many more activities including making a bill of materials and contact vendors were done once it was time for full-scale development. Challenges encountered along the journey and our way of overcoming these challenges are also discussed.

Keywords: PBL, Thesis, AGVs, Smart factory, Material handling systems.

1 Introduction

As industries move forward to the Industry 4.0 era, the demand for huge batch sizes will vary and the concept of focusing on each order as a unique event is introduced (Ghadiri, 2007). To adapt to these new trends, the factories must adapt to varying demands from customers, by improving its flexibility in handling small batch sizes in an efficient way. For an industry to be flexible enough, there are various factors to be considered. Among these factors, the importance of having a flexible material work flow for short production cycles as well as just in time supply chains in an industrial manufacturing environment can be shown (Künemund et al, 2014). Therefore, material handling systems within the factory plays an important role in improving the flexibility of a factory. One common practice in material handling system is to use automated mobile robots to do the transportation. These robots are generally called as Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs). Usage of these AGVs in a manufacturing system environment offers an efficient and a flexible material handling system which will result in an increase in production output of the manufacturing process (Esmaili, 2007).

It is clear that there is much room for improvement in the field of material handling systems for Industry 4.0 era. Even though AGVs are the ideal candidate for building a flexible material handling system for industries, there are doubts about its application to a smart factory, simply because the current concepts behind existing AGVs are technologically inferior compared with the technological developments achieved by other aspects when we focus on meeting the requirements for Industry 4.0 (<https://ottomotors.com/blog/industry-4-0-flexible-agv>). But, by redesigning the AGVs, there is still potential for the AGVs to be applicable for the future of industry.

The first author had the opportunity to be in a team involved in building a Smart Learning Future Factory, related to the Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Industry (MSIE4.0) was funded by the Erasmus+ Curriculum Development program. This enabled in bringing forth concepts and ideas of AGV design and development to a real-world Smart Factory, by designing and developing 5 prototype AGVs specifically built for the Smart Factory at AIT (Asian Institute of Technology, Thailand). The developed prototype AGVs were used in the Master Thesis of the first author, on "Design and Development of a Hybrid

Fleet Management System for Automated Guided Vehicles”, and the algorithm developed for the Thesis is applied in the Smart Factory at the time of writing this article. For the years to come, these prototype AGVs and the infrastructure built around them will help engineering students to learn and develop skills related to Industry 4.0.

2 Identification of requirements

Upon receiving the opportunity to be a part of the team that built the Smart Future Learning Factory at AIT, the first author was assigned to work on the Material Handling System that was to be built to the Smart Factory. The requirements of the team leader were specified. The Material Handling system should be flexible, the control of the MHS should be remotely accessible from anywhere in the world and the MHS should be a learning platform for IE students to learn from. Having received full freedom to carry out concept development and after careful study of what need to be done in order to meet the specified requirements, an initial concept was developed. The idea of using Automate Guided Vehicles (AGVs) was proposed to the team. After a careful feasibility study, the team leader requested a scaled-down prototype of the concept AGV to be built and tested.

3 Design learning experience

After receiving approval for the proposed concept, it was time to design the scaled-down prototype of the AGVs. The initial AGV prototype design phase began after research was done on existing AGVs. Different AGV types were researched upon and their pros and cons were identified. Decisions on what sort of navigation method (Fixed path or free ranging) to be used was researched upon. Research done on using camera vision for free ranging capability received a negative feedback (Jian et al, 2006), where the problems associated with using camera vision was pointed out. Knowledge on why cameras are not favourable in gathering relevant data for applications involving transport solutions (Miljković et al, 2013) further solidified the stance in not using camera vision for AGV navigation. Upon researching on whether to use centralized or decentralized control (Künemund et al, 2014), researchers have pointed out the difficulties related to the operation of a centralized fleet of AGVs (Svestka & Overmars, 1998). After developing a sensible work plan, the small prototype AGV was developed and put to extensive testing (figure 1). Experiments were conducted in various aspects of the AGV in order to prove the proposed concept was a feasible one, and that it will meet the required specifications.

Figure 1: The initial prototype CAD drawing built to check the feasibility of operation in the factory floor

After seeing the potential of the proposed system and that the concept was feasible, reliable, repeatable and reproduceable upon implementation to the smart factory, green light was received to move ahead with the development of the full scaled AGVs. The scope of the project was changed in order to develop five AGV units. After re-evaluating the design specifications according to the experience gained by the scaled-down prototype,

the CAD design of the full-scaled AGV began. Adhering to the required payload capacity, the required dimensions and other relevant data, the CAD drawing was completed (figure 2).

Figure 2: The final designed CAD drawings of the full scaled AGVs

The next step in the design phase was the electronics of the AGVs. A printed circuit board was designed specially for the AGVs. By doing this, all the electronics of the AGV was securely fastened to one circuit board which will avoid unnecessary wiring being done on AGVs.

4 Project management learning experience

By this time of the development phase, the design of the final AGV and the PCB (Printed Circuit Board) was finalized. All the major components needed for both the AGV and the PCB were decided upon and it was time to move on with the purchase of needed components. Due to the requirement of doing one-time purchases from a vendor, the team leader advised to perform the orders methodically, to avoid possible re-orders. Due to this reason, a comprehensive list of materials was created on the purchase items for both the AGVs, PCBs and all other required items. This list of materials was grouped and clustered according to the availability for different vendors, for the ease of purchasing. The cost estimation for the entire project was created upon request and was submitted to the team leader.

The list of material was sent to multiple vendors in order to identify the most suitable vendor who provided the best value for money. After contacting the vendors and checking the relevant information such as estimated date of delivery, the purchases were made according to the urgency of the said items. Some items were not available domestically. Hence, these purchases were given a higher priority to avoid delays associated with delivery. Permission was taken from the team leader to make purchases from overseas as soon as possible. The next most urgent items related to the mechanical structure were then purchased, followed by the electronic components.

The very first items to be received were items related to the mechanical structure. The aluminium frame for the five AGVs were quickly built and tested for strength. Thanks to the timely purchases, the PCBs which was shipped from China was delivered just as the electronic items were delivered. Hence, the time spent in waiting for the rest of the items to be delivered were well spent in completing the PCBs. At the end of this phase, the PCBs were tried and tested and was ready to be fixed to the AGVs.

The next delivery was the mecanum wheels and the motors, which was ordered from the same vendor. By this time, the main components of the AGV were ready to be assembled (figure 3). The progress was shown to the team leader and the initial tests revealed that the AGVs were performing as expected in the Smart Factory.

Figure 3: The AGV in its aluminium frame with the electronics assembled.

The shipment from United States took much longer than expected. These were the Magnetic Guide Sensors and their accessories to be used in fixed path AGV navigation. But the time spent waiting was well utilized by testing the AGV fleet management algorithm developed by the first author, which was to be used in the Smart Future Learning Factory.

Finally, after receiving all the components, assembling them and after extensive testing carried out to ensure a reliable performance, the outer acrylic plastic body was put to production. The outer plastic body was delivered within a week, and was fixed to the AGVs. Finally, the AGVs got the appearance of a mobile robot (figure 4).

Figure 4: A completed AGV at the end of the development.

5 Implementation learning experience

Extensive testing was done from the now operational AGVs. Tests on accuracy and repeatability of navigation were conducted. The AGVs were tuned in order to get maximum accuracy possible. During these tests, the navigational flexibility of the mecanum wheels were also tested. The mecanum wheels offered much more manoeuvrability than traditional wheels. They helped the AGV navigate sideways and rotate on the spot beside the normal navigational methods. Therefore, by using these tests, an algorithm was developed which offered accurate, robust and flexible navigational capability to the AGVs.

The next phase was to develop a reliable communication platform. The AGVs communicated via standard Wi-Fi, and so, the AGVs connected to the existing Local Area Network (LAN) of the Laboratory. By doing so, the communication links with the main control computer was made easy and fast without the need of purchasing additional communication hardware.

By the mid of March, the five full-scaled AGVs were ready to be deployed on the Smart Future Learning Factory. Modifications were made to the factory floor in order for the AGVs to do its navigations. The AGVs were ready to be linked with the Hybrid Fleet management system. Table 1 shows the dates and milestones of the project.

Table 1. Milestones and important dates.

Date	Milestones
October 1, 2019	Initial design sketches for the AGV
October 4, 2019	Beginning of the CAD design
October 9, 2019	Creating the Bill of Materials
October 16, 2019	Finalizing the CAD design
October 18, 2019	Initial design of the PCB
November 1, 2019	Finalizing the List of Parts and Bill of Materials
November 2, 2019	Finalizing the PCB design
November 3, 2019	Initial sketchup of algorithm and coding
November 13, 2019	First successful communication link-up using TCP-PI protocol
November 18, 2019	Begin work on JavaScript coding
November 22, 2019	Receiving the PCBs. Started PCB soldering
December 03, 2019	Start building the mechanical framework for the AGVs
December 23, 2019	Finished the build of the mechanical frameworks for all 5 AGVs
January 02, 2020	Start assembling the basic electronics assembly for all 5 AGVs
January 15, 2020	Finished assembling the basic electronics for all 5 AGVs
January 16, 2020	First day of controlling multiple AGVs simultaneously
February 2, 2020	Initial design of the Graphical User Interface for the main server
February 11, 2020	The arrival of the final components for the AGVs, the magnetig guide sensors and its peripherals
February 18, 2020	Fixing the Acrylic bodies to the AGVs.
March 4, 2020	Optimizing the communication links
March 12, 2020	Deployment of all 5 AGVs simultaneously on the factory floor
March 17, 2020	Initial AGV fleet management algorithm development
March 22, 2020	Completion of the AGV fleet management algorithm
April 2, 2020	Optimizing the Digital Inertial Measuring system for increased navigational accuracies
April 6, 2020	Final completion date of improving all the AGV algorithms
April 22, 2020	AGVs are deployed in the Smart Factory successfully.

The AGVs had a fast, robust and a very resilient bi-communication platform from which information was shared between the AGVs and the computer. The cloud robotics platform was an ideal solution to integrating wireless links between multiple units (Aniruddha Singhal et al, 2017). Research was carried out on possible methods of AGV fleet management. Research done on how to handle robots in a public environment was referred (Causse

& L. H. Pampagnin, 1995), since the AGVs will operate on a factory floor where humans will also work. Also, challenges that arise in managing multiple robots in a constricted environment was also looked at (R.Alami et al, 1998) to gain knowledge on how to approach the development of the algorithm. Possible methods of localization were researched upon. Methods such as using navigation signs in order to locate the robots (Jian, 2006) and usage of image sign tags replacing magnetic tags (Lu, 2001) were compelling methods. But, finally the use of RFID tags placed on the floor to act as the method of AGV localization was carried out.

The final AGV fleet management algorithm had the capability of directing the AGVs to workstations situated in the smart factory and deliver items from the source to the destination. Due to the capability of the AGV to do a hybrid navigation, where it switches between fixed path navigation at the vicinity of each workstation and switches to free ranging navigation on its way to the destination, the AGVs had the best of both worlds, the excellent navigational accuracy of a fixed path system with the flexibility and ease of modifications offered from free ranging systems.

When developing the decentralized operation, the necessary machine-to-machine communication, their important protocols and relevant information was researched upon (Clark et al, 2003). It was a necessity to build up a dynamic database of information where each AGV can read and write data. This database act as the information hub from which the AGVs will store all the important information such as AGV status, current position, etc.

6 Challenges encountered along the journey

The path to development of the prototype AGVs was filled with unexpected challenges, obstacles. But the entire project was successfully completed by solving one problem at a time. The biggest problem encountered was the great unevenness of the factory floor. The floor not so slippery and smooth, ideal for mecanum wheels. But it was extremely uneven that the first prototype AGV had so much trouble in travelling straight. From the tests done on the prototype, it was clear that this problem will affect to the full-scaled AGVs as well. Hence, a digital gyroscope with a high rate of data retrieval was used along with a dedicated microcontroller for it. By this way, any unwanted changes in orientation of the AGV when it is operating will soon be detected and necessary steps will be taken instantaneously.

7 Conclusion and the learning experience gained from the project

The learning experience gained from this project is so immense that by the end of the project, skills in both academic and non-academic sides was achieved. Knowledge on Information and Communication technology and many other fields of engineering such as designing PCBs, experience in mechanical engineering, experience in electrical and electronics engineering, experience in computer programming was gained. Apart from these academic knowledges gained, knowledge on how to act responsibly from a working point of view, experience in contacting vendors and placing orders and dealing with payments and deliveries and delays and many more life skills were achieved.

Acknowledgements

This work is the outcome of project "Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0)" that has been funded with support from the European Commission (Project Number: 586137-EPP-1-2017-1-TH-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP). This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

8 References

Alami, R., Fleury, S., Herrb, M., Ingrand, F. and Robert, F., "Multi-robot cooperation in the MARTHA project," in IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 36-47, March 1998, doi: 10.1109/100.667325.

- Causse, O. and Pampagnin, L. H., "Management of a multi-robot system in a public environment," Proceedings 1995 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems. Human Robot Interaction and Cooperative Robots, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, 1995, pp. 246-252 vol.2, doi: 10.1109/IROS.1995.526168.
- Clark, C. M., Rock, S. M., and Latombe, J., "Motion planning for multiple mobile robots using dynamic networks," 2003 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (Cat. No.03CH37422), Taipei, Taiwan, 2003, pp. 4222-4227 vol.3, doi: 10.1109/ROBOT.2003.1242252.
- Jian, L. U., Hiroyasu, I. & Kyoko, H., (2006) A Hybrid Vision Method for Autonomous Guided Vehicle Navigation
- Khanmohammadi, S., Ghadiri, H. and Jahedmotlagh, M. R., "Modelling of helper robots in manufacturing systems using Petri Nets," 2008 IEEE International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IEEE World Congress on Computational Intelligence), Hong Kong, 2008, pp. 1692-1697, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN.2008.4634025.
- Mehdi, E., "Intelligent path planning of AGV systems." *Tabriz university* (2007).
- Miljković, Z., Vuković, N., Mitić, M. & Babić, B. (2013) New hybrid vision-based control approach for automated guided vehicles
- Singhal, A., Aniruddha & Pallav, Prasun & Kejriwal, Nishant & Choudhury, Soumyadeep & Kumar, Swagat & Sinha, Rajesh. (2017). Managing a fleet of autonomous mobile robots (AMR) using cloud robotics platform. 1-6. 10.1109/ECMR.2017.8098721.
- Svestka, P. & Overmars, M. H., (1998) Coordinated path planning for multiple robots. In: Robotics and Autonomous Systems 23
- Wissing, M., Kuenemund, F., Hess, D. and Roehrig, C., "Hybrid Navigation System for Mecanum Based Omnidirectional Automated Guided Vehicles," *ISR/Robotik 2014; 41st International Symposium on Robotics*, Munich, Germany, 2014, pp. 1-6.